

was highest with common carp (71.4%), and lowest with rohu (48.1%) (see table). Weight increase of common carp was 13.07 times initial weight. Weights of other species increased 4.91-6.80 times. Although the rice area was reduced

14%, there was little difference in grain yield from plots with fish (4.6 t/ha) and control plots (4.7 t/ha). The additional cost incurred in raising fingerlings (preparation of trench, fish stock, feed, labor) was \$485/ha per 100 d. (Only

10% of the cost of trench preparation is taken to calculate cost of one season). The total return from fish yield was \$751/ha per 100 d. Net return was \$266/ha per 100 d. □

Rice-based crop rotations for upland fields

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Upland crop rotations were tried 1980-81 under partially irrigated conditions at the Regional Research Station, Semiliguda, Koraput (884 m, 18°20' N, 82°30' E) in a randomized block design with 4 replications. Short-duration rice was direct sown during the wet season under rainfed conditions, followed by wheat cultivar Utkalika, gardenpea Bonneville, chickpea JG62, mustard M-27, and potato Kufri Chandramukhi in the dry season (DS). Rice varieties used were OR 165-24-12 in 1980 and Culture-I in 1981, both with 90 d duration.

The rice received 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha in 1980 and 40-9-17 kg in 1981. DS crops received the recommended package of practices. The soil was red clay loam with 5.1 pH, EC 0.168 dS/m, 0.68% organic C, 0.06% total N, 5 kg available P, and 320 kg available K/ha.

Highest yield (20.9 t/ha) was with rice - potato (see table). Rice - potato also was most efficient. Single crop rice was the most inefficient. Highest net profit was with rice - potato (see figure). □

Efficiency of crop rotations under partially irrigated conditions. Semiliguda, India, 1980-81.

Crop rotation	Yield (t/ha)		Protein ^a (t/ha)	Carbohydrate ^a (t/ha)	Energy ^a (MJ × 10 ³ /ha)
	Wet season	Dry season			
Rice - fallow	1.9	—	0.1	1.0	18.2
Rice - wheat	1.7	3.0	0.4	3.0	59.0
Rice - gardenpea (green pod)	1.7	2.5	0.2	1.1	21.4
Rice - chickpea	1.7	0.7	0.2	1.3	26.8
Rice - mustard	1.7	0.8	0.1	1.1	34.4
Rice - potato	2.0	18.9	0.4	4.7	84.3

^aProtein, carbohydrate, and energy components were calculated for edible portions only, per standards fixed by the National Institute of Nutrition (ICMR), Hyderabad, India.

Efficiency of crop rotations in terms of net profit. Semiliguda, India, 1980-81.

Zinc required for a rice - wheat sequence in alkali soils

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We evaluated Zn levels needed for a rice - wheat crop rotation in field experiments in the alkali soils of

Kumarganj. Experimental fields had pH 10.2-10.4, ESP 70-90 and EC 2-2.5 mmho/cm in 1:2 soil-water suspension. Gypsum (14% S) at 12 t or pyrite (30% S) at 4.5 t/ha had been added to improve soil conditions before the first rice crop in 1976. Plot size was 6 × 3.5 m in a randomized block design with 4 replications.

Short-duration semidwarf Pusa 2-21 was transplanted at 15 × 15 cm with 4-

Table 1. Zn requirement of transplanted rite Pusa 2-21 in alkali soils of Kumarganj, India.

Zn (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha) at foliar spray intervals of		
	1 wk	2 wk	3 wk
0	0.6	0.5	0.9
3.4	1.71.5		1.1
6.8	2.52.2		1.7
10.0	2.1	3.4	2.9
LSD (0.05)	0.3		